

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Ahmadi, R., & Akbari, M. R. (2024). Social Harms of Child Labor in Afghanistan (Case Study of Bamyan City). *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(2), 186-203.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.02.497

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Social Harms of Child Labor in Afghanistan (Case Study of Bamyan City)

Ramazan Ahmadi¹, Mohammad Reza Akbari²

¹ Sociology Department, Social Sciences Faculty, Bamyan University, Bamyan, Afghanistan.

² Sociology Department, Social Sciences Faculty, Bamyan University, Bamyan, Afghanistan. Email: rezaakbari3050@gmail.com. ORCID: 0009-0004-3452-2701

Correspondence: Ramazan Ahmadi, Sociology Department, Social Sciences Faculty, Bamyan University, Bamyan, Afghanistan. Tel: +93779524902. E-mail: Ramazan.ahmadi230@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0002-8299-7080

Abstract

The social harms of child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, represent a fundamental and critical issue with widespread negative impacts on both children and society. Due to poverty and economic difficulties, children are compelled to undertake hard and exhausting work, depriving them of their basic rights such as education and play. The aim of this study is to identify the factors influencing child employment, evaluate its social and psychological consequences, and provide effective solutions to reduce and eliminate these harms. This quantitative research gathered information using questionnaires from child labor in Bamyan City and analyzed it with SPSS software. The results show that half of the children are deprived of education and mostly work in mechanics and blacksmithing with low income. Their guardians are predominantly unemployed or day laborers, and these children live in large families. The primary reasons for child employment include poverty, unemployment, the need for skill acquisition, deprivation from school, and the incapacity or illness of parents. Child labor leads to serious social harms such as depression, hopelessness, illness, aggression, encouragement towards drug use and crimes, and sexual abuse. Some children feel hopeless about the future, while others have aspirations such as becoming skilled workers, doctors, engineers, and politicians. This situation requires serious and urgent measures.

Keywords: Social Harms, Child Labor, Poverty, Unemployment, Bamyan

1. Introduction

Children are considered the future of any society and are among a nation's resources. However, in many countries, children face numerous issues and challenges that directly impact their lives and future. One of these challenges is child labor, which occurs in many countries, including Afghanistan, as a significant social harm. Child labor is a global phenomenon that comes in various forms and types. According to the International Labor Organization (ILO), child labor refers to activities that harm the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of children and deprive them of their right to education. For example, it may result in children being deprived of school, forced to

drop out, or required to perform heavy and lengthy work alongside their studies (International Labor Organization, 2017). A 2018 ILO report indicates that approximately 218 million children worldwide are engaged in some form of labor. Based on this report, it can be said that one out of every ten children globally is a child laborer. According to the ILO, Sub-Saharan African countries have the highest number of child labor. In 2018, 29% of children aged five to seventeen in this region were engaged in labor, most of them in hazardous and harmful work. The situation is different in the Middle East and North African countries, where about 5% of children aged five to seventeen are involved in dangerous work. However, in Southeast Asian countries, the child labor situation is alarming; in countries like India and Pakistan, many children are sold or kidnapped to be exploited in farms, factories, and workshops under harsh working conditions (Corsaro, 2014).

Bamyan, as one of the important and strategic areas in central Afghanistan, is known for its historical and cultural heritage and is considered a vital part of the country. However, like other regions of Afghanistan, Bamyan faces social and economic challenges that significantly impact the lives of young people, especially children. Among these challenges is the issue of child labor in Bamyan city, which is considered a social harm in the region. In Afghanistan, particularly in regions like Bamyan that suffer from inadequate economic and social infrastructure, child labor emerges as a serious issue. Poverty, unemployment, security crises, and other factors stemming from weak economic and social conditions compel children to engage in economic activities.

This article aims to examine and analyze the social harms of child labor in Bamyan city, Afghanistan. These harms include physical and psychological factors, lack of education, safety and health risks in the work environment, creating social and economic gaps, and long-term impacts on the children's social and economic future. Additionally, this research will investigate the rights of children and their violations in the workplace and attempt to provide solutions to support the rights of child labor and improve their living conditions.

2. Problem Statement

Child labor, as a subject that seriously impacts social and human aspects in less developed societies, is a significant and concerning challenge in Bamyan city, Afghanistan. This issue involves multidimensional social harms that directly affect the lives and futures of children.

Child labor in Bamyan city, due to poor economic conditions and weak social and economic infrastructure, is forced to engage in various economic activities. These activities include work in agriculture, small industries, domestic work, and even hazardous jobs. These children, at an age when they should be studying and playing, are exposed to hard and unhealthy working conditions. One crucial aspect of the child labor issue in Bamyan city is the physical, psychological, and social consequences that these children experience due to the inhumane working conditions they endure. The stress and fatigue from heavy work and unsafe conditions can directly harm their physical and mental health.

In this context, the violation of children's rights is also a fundamental concern in the problem statement. Children have basic rights to education, health, learning, and a favorable childhood experience. However, their presence in the workplace in Bamyan city conflicts with these rights, especially in cases involving hazardous work and underage employment, making these violations more evident.

Consequently, the issue of child labor in Bamyan city, Afghanistan, is a multidimensional problem with social, economic, and legal complexities, raising concerns and immediate needs for protecting these children's rights and improving their living conditions. This research will add valuable insights into social and legal concerns and aid in effective social interaction and policymaking to support child labor in Bamyan city.

3. Importance and Necessity of the Research

Research on the social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, is highly significant and can contribute to the sustainable social and economic development of the region and the country as a whole. This

research can have numerous positive impacts on the lives of children, families, and society from various perspectives:

3.1 Children's Rights

One of the primary importance of this research is the preservation and promotion of children's rights. Basic rights of children to education, health, hygiene, and social support are guaranteed. This research can help identify the violations of these rights in the workplace and various social spheres, providing necessary information for reforming policies and support programs.

3.2 Social and Economic Development

Children's involvement in economic activities can have profound effects on the social and economic development of the region. On one hand, this issue can lead to a reduction in children's education and skills, eventually resulting in a shortage of skilled human resources in the region's future. On the other hand, the presence of children in the workforce can decrease economic productivity and increase future unemployment rates. This research can provide a more precise understanding of the economic and social impacts of child labor on the region.

3.3 Health and Hygiene

Harsh and dangerous working conditions may directly negatively impact children's health and hygiene. Research in this area can help identify the safety and health risks children face and propose appropriate measures to safeguard their health.

3.4 Psychological Impacts

Inappropriate working conditions and mental and emotional pressures may lead to irreversible psychological effects on children. This research can help identify the psychological impacts of these conditions on children and provide strategies to improve their mental health.

3.5 Continuity of Education

Children's presence in the workplace can result in lost educational opportunities and personal development. Research in this area can identify educational barriers faced by child labor and propose measures to enhance their education and personal development.

In conclusion, this research will not only help identify and analyze the social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, but also provide strategies and solutions to improve the living conditions of these children and promote the sustainable development of the region.

4. Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to examine and analyze the social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan. Based on this overarching goal, the specific objectives of the research are as follows:

- Identify the types of work that children in Bamyan City engage in and determine the type and severity of associated safety and health hazards.
- Investigate the physical and psychological harm caused by child labor on children's health and development, especially in physical, emotional, and psychological aspects.

- Analyze the impact of involvement in economic activities on child laborers' education and educational growth, and the violation of their educational rights.
- Assess the impact of child labor on their social access and future opportunities, including future employment and economic disparities.
- Evaluate the extent to which child labor' rights are upheld in the workplace and identify weaknesses and violations of these rights as per international laws and standards.
- Provide recommendations and strategies to improve the conditions of child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, including enhancing safety and health in the workplace, developing educational programs, and promoting social and economic support and the enforcement of children's rights.
- Raise public awareness and understanding of the issues and social harms faced by child labor and the importance of addressing the rights of this vulnerable group.

Overall, this research aims to improve the situation of child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, by analyzing and examining their social harms, advocating for their basic rights, and creating better conditions for their growth and development.

5. Research Question

Main Research Question: What social and economic factors lead to the increase in the number of child labor in Bamyan City, and what types of social and psychological harms do these children face?

This question aims to examine the roots and reasons for the spread of the child labor phenomenon in Bamyan and its impacts on the lives and futures of these children.

Sub-questions:

What are the various forms of child labor?

What factors cause children to work in different jobs?

What are the consequences of child labor in various jobs?

What risks and challenges do children face in different occupations?

What percentage of child labor attend school, and how many drop out?

6. Research Hypothesis

Main Hypothesis: Poverty and lack of financial resources in families are the main factors increasing the number of child labor in Bamyan City, and due to unsuitable working conditions, these children face significant physical, psychological, and social harms.

This hypothesis suggests a relationship between the economic status of families and the number of child labor, examining the negative impacts of work on children from various aspects.

Sub-hypotheses:

Children are engaged in hard and strenuous work, from being mechanics' apprentices to working as bakery assistants in the marketplace.

The weak economic situation of families is the main factor driving children to work.

Working leads to a decrease in school attendance and an increase in dropout rates among children.

Child labor causes psychological problems, including depression and anxiety, in children.

Child labor face discrimination and unfavorable behavior within the community and among their peers and are at risk of being used in illegal activities.

7. Literature Review

The social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City is a relatively new research topic. Afghan researchers have not yet conducted studies on this issue in Bamyan, and there has been insufficient research at the national level in Afghanistan. However, international organizations have conducted research on this topic outside Afghanistan. Here are some summarized reports and studies:

According to a report by UNICEF, participation in economic activities can lead to a lack of education and delays in children's educational progress. Studies indicate that child labor have lower education rates compared to their peers (UNICEF, 2017). Moreover, child labor in heavy and hazardous industries such as mining and construction face serious safety and health risks, and the lack of adherence to health and safety standards can lead to irreversible accidents for them. Additionally, children's involvement in informal and hazardous economic activities can create social and economic gaps in the future. These children often end up in low-skilled and low-income jobs due to lack of education and insufficient work experiences (ILO, 2017).

Kayen conducted a study in Afghanistan. This research examines the impact of child labor, prevalent in two of Afghanistan's most populous provinces (Nangarhar and Kabul), on children's development. According to this study, child labor in Afghanistan significantly negatively affects children's growth. The study suggests that physical immaturity leads to weakened immune systems, malnutrition, bodily pains, and other issues. In this context, working children are more susceptible to illness compared to their non-working peers and are considered risk factors for themselves and society. Afghan children who work show signs of forgetfulness, overthinking, and lack of logical reasoning compared to their non-working peers. Child labor has caused Afghan children to neglect their social and emotional lives. Most of these children are unaware of the importance of socializing and making friends, display antisocial tendencies, and engage in illegal activities as they grow older. Even in interviews with the researcher, these working children expressed no concern about missing class or resembling non-working children (Kayen, 2023).

The ACSOR-Surveys Institute conducted research on child labor in Afghanistan in 2008. One notable finding of this research is the relationship between child labor and education. In Afghanistan, the current school attendance rate for children aged 5 to 17 is 58.7 percent. Although those who do not attend school generally work more hours than those who do, participation in child labor does not seem to negatively impact children's educational outcomes overall, as measured by current school attendance, school enrollment, or academic achievements. Regarding entry into child labor, most working children in four provinces reported that their father had the most influence on obtaining their current job, although a significant portion said that no one actually influenced them. The primary reason adults in the child labor's family allow children to work is related to the family's economic situation, usually to provide supplementary income. Finally, respondents were asked their opinions on the support needed to address the issue of child labor. Recommendations can be categorized into three general groups: improving education or the school environment, improving the economic status of the family and children, and creating a safe environment (ACSOR-Surveys, 2008).

In 2014, Salahuddin Naderi, in his thesis titled "Public Sociology and Testing Castells' Theory in the Field of Child Labor (A Participatory Action Research with Afghan Children in the Moshtaq Child-Friendly Center)," studied the situation of Afghan children. He used Manuel Castells' theory to depict the situation of children, illustrating conditions where children fall into a state of no return, referred to as black holes. Among these, migrant children are always at greater risk of falling into these black holes compared to other children. The goal of public sociology is to help these individuals and familiarize them with their conditions. This study used a project-based approach and a child-to-child approach to carry out activities aimed at educating, raising awareness, and empowering children. In the research process, 23 girls and 33 boys collaborated at the Moshtaq Child-Friendly Center (Naderi, 2014).

Pir-Khandan and colleagues, in their research, believe that many children work under exploitative conditions and are subjected to exploitation in a way that not only hinders their education but also has numerous negative effects on their physical and mental health. In addition to having weaker and more vulnerable bodies to work-related injuries and illnesses, these children also have little knowledge and awareness of the dangers of work, which makes them less likely to take care of themselves. Child labor exposes them to many social harms. The inefficiency of

educational, welfare, and economic institutions exposes this group to risks that, if continued, will have irreparable costs for society and the country (Pir-Khandan et al., 2021).

In 2012, Tawallai and colleagues, in their article “The Relationship Between Child Labor and Human Development in Developing and Underdeveloped Countries,” examined the phenomenon of child labor and the human development index. They argue that countries with high human development indices have lower rates of child labor, and conversely, where the rate of child labor is higher, the human development index is lower. This study examined the relationship between child labor and human development in 65 developing and underdeveloped countries. The findings indicate that the higher the human development index, the lower the rate of child labor, and vice versa. The researchers also concluded that achieving a high human development index, directly related to the quality of human life, requires the reduction and eradication of child labor in societies (Tawallai, 2012).

Zare Shahabadi conducted research in Yazd Province, Iran, on the role of dysfunctional families in the phenomenon of child labor. The findings of the study indicate that factors such as the unemployment of the family head, economic poverty of families, domestic violence, lack of healthy role models in the behavior of parents towards each other and the child, and parental addiction have contributed to the emergence of child labor. Among these factors, parental violence towards the child and parental violence towards each other had the greatest impact on the occurrence of this phenomenon (Zare Shah Abadi et al., 1988).

In 2019, Ali Imanzadeh, in his article “Lived Experience of child labor in Tabriz City from the Feeling of Loneliness,” conducted a descriptive and explanatory study of the lived experiences of child labor and their feelings of loneliness. This qualitative, phenomenological study, using purposive sampling and in-depth interviews with fifteen child labor, identified four main themes from their experiences: “perceived feelings,” “types of loneliness,” “consequences of loneliness,” and “ways to overcome loneliness.” child labor experience various types of loneliness, particularly existential loneliness, and feel a sense of meaninglessness, hopelessness, and abandonment in their lives. The study suggests policies such as improving social interactions, providing educational opportunities, teaching social skills, and spiritual therapy to overcome these feelings in child labor (Imanzadeh, 2019).

Shahin’s research on child labor shows that there are various reasons why children enter the workforce. The most important reasons include poverty, the high costs of education, and the fact that some families consider education unnecessary and prefer their children to enter the labor market at a young age (Shahin, 2012).

In 2017, Driscoll, in his article “A Review of Child Labor in Small-Scale Industry and Mining in Asia and Africa,” conducted a rapid review of data from academic, policy, and NGO sources about child labor in small-scale mining and industry (ASM) in Asia and Africa. The article describes various types of child labor in mines in countries such as Tanzania, the Philippines, and Indonesia, including pit digging, underground work, ore hauling and crushing, cooking for adults, and selling goods and services to adults, all of which pose various physical and psychological harms (O’Driscoll, 2017).

8. Methodology

This research is applied in terms of its purpose and descriptive-analytical in nature and method. To conduct the study on the social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, a quantitative methodology with an emphasis on field study (Survey) and the use of questionnaires as the primary data collection tool was employed. This method, as one of the quantitative research tools, allows for the collection of extensive data, reflecting the overall status of the social harms experienced by child labor in Bamyan City. The statistical population of this research includes child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, encompassing 142 child labor. A simple random sampling method was used to select the sample. Data were collected through questionnaires in July 2023.

The survey data collected in this study were analyzed using the SPSS program. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, and arithmetic mean, as well as parametric tests, were used in the data analysis. The reliability of the scales was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient is a commonly used test to measure internal reliability. The calculated alpha coefficient ranges from 1, indicating perfect internal reliability, to 0, indicating no internal reliability (Bryman, 2008). A level of 0.70 is considered satisfactory (Mohammadbeigi et al., 2015). Brthout (2000) indicated that a level of 0.60 is "good" and that a health index used in BHPS reached a level of 0.77 (Bryman, 2008). In this study, the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient for Likert-type questions was found to be 0.769. The obtained results indicate that the questionnaire form used in the survey has sufficient reliability.

Quantitative research on the social harms faced by child labor in Bamyan City, Afghanistan, using questionnaires allows us to identify and analyze the multiple effects of social harms on this group of the population. The results of this research can serve as a basis for adopting appropriate measures and strategies to reduce and prevent the social harms experienced by child labor in this significant region.

9. Child Labor: Harms and Challenges

The term "child labor" refers to individuals under the age of 18 who participate in economic and work activities. These activities can include agricultural work, domestic work, employment in small industries and productions, street work, and public space work, as well as hazardous and essential jobs. Statistics show that child labor is extensively employed in developing countries. This concerning reality is not only due to the harmful physical and psychological impacts on children but also due to the violation of the human rights of this vulnerable group.

According to the theoretical classification by the International Labor Organization (ILO), child labor includes children engaged in the worst forms of child labor or those working below the minimum legal working age. They may also be forced to combine school attendance with excessively long and heavy work hours (ILO, 2017). Child labor are children who work outside the home. This type of activity encompasses a wide range of both real and bogus work, unskilled labor, begging, shoe-shining, selling low-value goods, and more (Imani & Nersisianous, 2010).

Child laborers, individuals under 18 years, engage in economic and work activities. This issue is a serious social harm in developing countries and has profound impacts on children's lives, society, and future societal development. The harms and challenges faced by this disadvantaged group include:

9.1 *Physical and Psychological Risks*

Child labor face serious physical risks due to hazardous working conditions and high physical demands. Heavy and exhausting work can cause significant physical health issues, including back pain, bone and joint problems, muscle weakness, and cuts and abrasions. Additionally, job stress and burdens can have negative psychological effects, such as increased stress, anxiety, and depression in these children.

9.2 *Lack of Education*

The work commitments of child labor limit their access to educational opportunities. These children often cannot adequately continue their education and, due to the poor economic conditions of their families, are forced to work, missing out on proper education.

9.3 *Social Isolation*

Child laborers are deprived of experiencing a normal social life due to their work conditions. They are usually excluded from participating in social activities, games, and educational and sports activities, leading to isolation and social marginalization.

9.4 Risk of Social Deviations

Child labor, due to a lack of access to proper educational opportunities and participation in social activities, is at risk of social deviations. They may engage in illegal and harmful activities due to harsh working conditions and economic pressures, resulting in negative experiences and harm to society.

9.5 Long-term Effects

The physical and psychological harms of child labor can have long-term effects on their lives. Physical injuries may lead to permanent health problems, and psychological harm can directly and indirectly affect their social relationships, education, and future careers.

10. Children's Rights: Violation of Fundamental Rights of Child Labor in Bamyan, Afghanistan

Children, as the leaders and future hope of any society, hold a crucial place in development and progress. Children's rights, as one of the fundamental principles of human rights, play a vital role in determining the fate of this young generation and the stability of society. These rights include fundamental rights such as the right to life, education, health and hygiene, social support, and more. However, the significant and often overlooked violation of children's rights in certain areas, especially in conditions of severe economic and social crises, causes serious harm to society.

The fact is that human rights belong to all human beings by virtue of their humanity, without any discrimination based on race, religion, color, nationality, language, class, creed, ethnic or social origin, political opinions, or any other reason, which is sufficient to refute this argument. Additionally, human rights, with their universal nature, apply to all age groups, and therefore children enjoy the same general human rights as adults (ILO, 20018).

Children's rights are simply human rights for children, with a special focus on the rights to special protection and care due to their vulnerability and inability to defend themselves. This is why the international community affirmed in 1989 that children have human rights and adopted the view that children need a special convention. The result was the adoption of the Convention on the Rights of the Child as the first international legal instrument to encompass a comprehensive set of human rights, including civil, political, economic, cultural, and social rights for children (ILO, 20018).

The Bamyan region in Afghanistan is one such area where children not only grapple with economic and social problems but also view entering the labor market as a solution to meet the financial needs of their families. However, meeting basic family needs through child labor results in the violation of the fundamental rights of this segment of society.

11. Finding

This study, being a quantitative research, collected data using questionnaires and performed statistical analysis. In this study, the absolute majority of participants were boys. Figure 1 shows that only one girl participated in the study, while the rest were boys.

Figure 1: Gender of Participants

In this study, children between the ages of 9 and 17 participated, with the detailed percentage shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Age of Participants

These children are present in various educational levels, as depicted in Figure 3, with the majority of children being students of secondary school.

Figure 3: Educational Level of Participants

This research indicates that more than 50 percent of children currently do not attend school and are deprived of education due to work, as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Access to School by Participants

Child labor are engaged in various tasks, and according to this study, most working children in Bamyan are occupied with difficult and strenuous tasks, as illustrated in Figure 5, which clearly shows the frequency of the types of work.

Figure 5: Jobs of Participants

Bamyan’s child labor have resorted to hard work due to economic difficulties, but Figure 6 indicates that these children do not have an acceptable income. The daily income of working children is expressed in Afghan currency units, which at the time of the survey was 87 Afghanis equivalent to 1 US dollar.

Figure 6: Daily Income of Child Labors

Most of the child labor have fathers, and the head of their family is their father. A small percentage of family heads are brothers, mothers of children, or others. Therefore, Figure 7 illustrates the family heads of child labor.

Figure 7: Head of the Family of Participants

Child labor is usually from poor family members, and the head of the family is mostly engaged in daily tasks. Figure 8 illustrates the duties of the head of the family.

Figure 8: The Job of the Head of Family

Child labors are usually from extended families, and the number of family members is mostly six or more than six individuals. Figure 9 depicts the number of family members in child labor.

Figure 9: The Number of Family Members

Children usually engage in laborious work due to economic difficulties, and Figure 10 clearly illustrates the reasons for work in childhood.

Figure 10: The Reason for Working in Childhood

Various factors have led children to engage in work, and Figure 11 illustrates the extent to which factors have compelled children to work and how each factor has affected them. This figure evaluates factors such as family economic problems, parental illness, insufficient income, domestic violence, and physical abuse.

Figure 11: Examining the Amount of Factors of Tendency or Forcing Children to Work (1)

Figure 12 illustrates the impact of factors such as providing educational facilities, parental coercion, parental divorce, migration, and increased unemployment on children’s compulsion to work.

Figure 12: Examining the Amount of Factors of Tendency or Forcing Children to Work (2)

Child labor usually face numerous challenges and endure various harms during their strenuous work. Figure 13 illustrates the difficulties encountered by children during work and the impacts it has on them.

Figure 13: Children Facing Problems in the Workplace (1)

Figure 14 also illustrates the damages and problems encountered by children during their work.

Figure 14: Children Facing Problems in the Workplace (2)

Every child has dreams and aspirations, desiring a better life in the future and holding various goals in mind. However, working children in the city of Bamyan have endured numerous social, mental, and physical damages, with their rights violated, engaged in laborious tasks beyond their capacity. These social damages have led some children to become indifferent towards their future, lacking aspirations. Figure 15 vividly portrays the aspirations

of child labor in the city of Bamyan, indicating which positions and roles they envision for themselves in the future.

Figure 15: The hope of children for Future

Children are the hope and future of a society and a nation. Education, upbringing, and addressing the needs of children while respecting their rights provide the groundwork for the healthy upbringing of adolescents and teenagers. Children will achieve the goals they set for their lives. The above figure illustrates that child labor has various aspirations; from skilled workers to the level of the president, they want to reach. However, these aspirations require that children receive education and that their basic rights are respected. Instead of hard labor, the focus should be on education, and families of child labor should be economically supported so that they are not forced to make their children work.

12. Conclusion

Child labor in the city of Bamyan, Afghanistan, face numerous social challenges and adversities that not only impact their individual lives but also have broader negative effects on society. These children often engage in labor from a young age due to poverty and family financial needs, leading to missed educational opportunities and hindered healthy development.

Research findings indicate that half of the children in Bamyan are deprived of education or do not attend school and are mostly engaged in laborious tasks. The most of these children work as apprentices in mechanical and ironwork sectors and hard and arduous works, yet they lack acceptable income. Their caregivers are often daily wage laborers or unemployed, and 91.5% of these children live in large families with six or more members. The most significant reasons for child employment, in order of priority, include poverty and economic hardships, unemployment, the need for skill training, deprivation from schooling, eagerness to work, migration, parental coercion, cooperation with parents, and parental incapacity or illness. Child labor carries serious social risks, as evidenced by the most prominent adversities faced by child labor, including depression, deprivation from childhood play, hopelessness, educational deprivation, work-related illness, aggression in the workplace,

encouragement to substance abuse, humiliation and ridicule by employers and people, encouragement to commit crimes and illegal activities, and physical harassment and abuse. These social adversities and mental health problems have led 31% of children to feel hopeless and aimless about their future. However, other children have aspirations for their future, including becoming skilled workers, mechanics, doctors, continuing their education, becoming engineers, teachers, wealthy individuals, government employees, family poverty alleviators, university professors, governors, politicians, presidents, judges, journalists, and educators of family members.

Therefore, the situation of child labor in Bamyan center not only violates their fundamental rights but also has widespread negative effects on society and sustainable development. Multiple social adversities, including the violation of children's rights, physical and mental health effects, decreased educational opportunities, and the creation of social and economic gaps, require serious and immediate measures to protect this vulnerable group. Considering the importance of children's rights and the negative impacts of violating these rights on the future of children and society, it is recommended that effective programs and policies be implemented to restrict and reduce child labor in Bamyan center. Additionally, ensuring financial resources and social participation for the development of educational programs and social support for child labor is of paramount importance. These actions can gradually reduce the chain of social adversities of child labor and guarantee the improvement of their living conditions and future.

Author Contributions: The first author, Ramazan Ahmadi conceived the theoretical framework, developed the formalism, conceptualization, methodology, Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing and data analyze. The second author, Mohammad Reza Akbari, administrated the field data collection and provided valuable contribution in revising the work.

Funding: This study was supported by a grant from the Afghanistan Research Initiative, University of Central Asia, funded by Canada's International Development Research Centre and the Aga Khan Foundation-Canada.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interests. As this research had no external source, there was no involvement of sponsor in the study's design, data collection, analysis, manuscript writing, or the decision to publish the result.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

References

- ACSOR-Surveys. (2008). Child Labor in Afghanistan: A Four-Province Study in Kabul, Kandahar, Nangarhar, and Balkh. *ICF International submitted to U.S. Department Labor*. Pp. 1-140.
- Bryman, A. (2008). *Social Research Methods*. New York: OXFORD University Press.
- Corsaro, W. A. (2014). *The Sociology of Childhood*. (Translated into Persian by Alireza Kermani and Masoud Rajabi Ardeshiri). Tehran: Sales.
- Imani, N. and Nersisianous, E. (2011). An Anthropological Study of the Phenomenon of Street Children in Karaj. *Social Issues in Iran*, 3(1), 7-32.
- Imanzadeh, A. and Alipour, S. (2019). Lived Experience of Loneliness by Tabriz's labor Children: A Phenomenological Study. *Iranian Journal of Social Studies and Research*, 8(2), 279-304.
- International Labor Organization (ILO). (2018). *Training Manual On Child Labour In Afghanistan*. Publications of the International Labour Office.
- ILO. (2017). Global estimates of child labour: Results and trends, 2012-2016. *Geneva: International Labour Organization Geneva*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/documents/publication/wcms_575499.pdf
- Kayen, H. S. (2023). The Impact of Child Labor on Children's Development: A Case Study Of Afghanistan. *Jurnal Bhineka Tunggal Ika*, Volume 10, Nomor 02, pp: 326-336.
- Mohammadbeigi, A., Mohammadsalehi, N., ve Aligol, M. (2015). Validity and Reliability of the Instruments and Types of Measurements in Health Applied Researches. *Journal of Rafsanjan University of Medical Sciences*. 13(12), 1153-1170.

- Naderi, S. (2014). Public Sociology and Testing Castells' Theory in the Context of Child Labor (Participatory Action Research with Afghan Children at the Moshtagh Child-Friendly Center). Sociology Department, Faculty of Literature and Social Sciences, University of Bahonar Kerman, *cited in Child Rights Support Association*, 2019, p. 88.
- O'Driscoll, D. (2017). *Overview of child labour in the artisanal and small-scale mining sector in Asia and Africa*. K4D Helpdesk Report. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies.
- Pir-Khandan, P., Parvin, S., & Siyahpour, F. (Year 8). Typology of Child Labor and its Detrimental Effects on Working Children in Tehran. *Social Work Research Journal*, Issue 28, pp: 115-158. doi.org/_10.22054/rjsw.2022.61472.502
- Shahin, L. (2012). Child Labor from Past to Present. *Journal of Social Sciences Research*, Gaziosmanpaşa University, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 103-118.
- Tawallai, H., Rafiei, H. and Beiglerian, A. (2009). The Relationship between Child Labor and Human Development in Underdeveloped and Developing Countries. *Social Welfare*, 9(35), 301-336.
- United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). (2017). Child Labour and Education—A Survey of Slum Settlements in Dhaka. <https://cdn.odi.org/media/documents/11145.pdf>
- Zare Shah Abadi, A., Haji Zadeh Mimandi, M., & Akbari Ghourtani, S. (2009). The Role of Dysfunctional Families in the Phenomenon of Child Labor (Case Study: Yazd Province). *Social Order Scientific-Research Quarterly*, Year 1, Issue 3, pp: 29-52.